

Karuna Satori's ASMR A Therapeutic Approach Among Teenagers - A Systematic Review

Srignana Lokesh Ezhil*

Research Scholar

sriganalokesh.e@vit.ac.in

Dept of Sensor and Biomedical Technology

Vellore Institute of Technology (VIT University), Vellore, India - 632014.

Abstract

Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response (ASMR) is the tingling sensation felt at the back of the spine to the neck, which induces a sleepy feel when a certain type of sound is heard. Methods - Databases such as Scopus, Google Scholar and PubMed were searched and analyzed. Karuna Satori's ASMR channel videos were watched and heard with earphones. The comment section of those videos were analyzed. Conclusion - The Systematic analysis indicates that Karuna Satori's ASMR videos are found to be therapeutic and are helping with the teenagers in reducing their stress, Depression and Anxiety levels.

Keywords

Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response

Introduction

Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response (ASMR) is the tingling sensation felt at the back of the spine to the neck, which induces a sleepy feel when a certain type of sound is heard [1]. ASMR is more deeply explained by Karuna Satori in her videos. There is a trigger test to determine which ASMR sounds will give a tingling sensation [2]. ASMR is a widespread and diversified sensory-affective phenomena. ASMR tendency appears to be rather regularly distributed among specialized and non-specialized samples. While many subjects reported a comparable set of sensory and relaxing effects, the experience does not appear to be uniform [3]. It should be noted that audio-visual triggers are neither required nor sufficient for ASMR induction. Prior study on real-life tactile ASMR triggers showed that they are widely accepted by ASMR responders. For example, 73% of ASMR-responders rated 'getting your hair brushed/played with' as an ASMR trigger, making it the second most commonly endorsed trigger after 'soft speaking,' which was endorsed by 74% of the sample, and significantly higher than prototypical visual (e.g., 'hand movements,' 48%) and auditory ('tapping,' 51%, 'scratching sounds,' 47%) ASMR triggers [4].

ASMR is a perceptual sensory phenomena, similar to meditation, in which people who are capable of experiencing it feel a pleasant and relaxing "tingling" sensation localized to the head and neck. Certain auditory and visual cues, such as whispering, personal attention, and even being the subject of a physician's clinical examination, cause these experiences. Individuals seeking to experience ASMR go to the website "YouTube," where videos utilizing these triggers have been created. Users typically view these films in a quiet location to experience the calming effect of ASMR [5]. Despite the general public's interest in ASMR, few scientific research have attempted to define the sorts of stimuli that most successfully trigger ASMR and how ASMR is connected to an individual's mental states and personality factors. Recent research has employed web-based surveys of the Big Five Inventory (BFI) to show that those with greater Openness and lower Conscientiousness ratings had more ASMR encounters. Such research, however, has an inherent sample selection bias in that subjects recruited over the internet may be more likely to divulge their ASMR experiences. Also, it is unclear how the stimulus properties were adjusted, which may have an effect on ASMR [6].

Methods

Databases such as Scopus, Google Scholar and PubMed were searched and analyzed. Karuna Satori's ASMR channel videos were watched and heard with earphones. The comment section of those videos were analyzed.

Summary

Karuna Satori the Mother of ASMR [11].

Karuna Satori has explained in her video the Origin of Fishbowl effect as - "The video for tonight is I finally finished! So, I tested out a trigger I dubbed "the fishbowl effect" a while back. Throughout the summer, I attend a lot of music festivals, and my very first one, I was a little "out of my mind" from feeding my brain haha. A man sat down next to me at a picnic table and began acting as if I were wearing a fishbowl on top of my head (as he said). He'd be speaking again every time he lifted his hands, and when he moved them back down, I couldn't hear him. It was a strange sensation, so I attempted it in one of our films" [7].

Figure 1.0. A 16 Minute Video of Fishbowl Effect by Karuna Satori [7].

Figure 1.1. A 21 Minute Video of Fishbowl effect used to improve tingle immunity [8].

Karuna Satori has quoted “Tonight's video wasn't simply pure ASMR; while the first half has ASMR triggers, it also addresses something that has recently hurt my feelings in the ASMR community. Please, if any makers are reading this, please do not take something so valuable to me. I never seek credit. I expect others to not take my tale and make it their own. In the meanwhile, please keep in mind that this movie is still as peaceful and tingling as ever, but I simply wanted to talk about it. Know that I adore you with all of my heart. I'll see you again tomorrow” [8].

She also found the reverse Fishbowl effect which is an amazing tingly feel.

Figure 1.2. A 23 Minute video of Reverse Fishbowl Effect [9].

Karuna Satori has quoted “I thought we might revisit a trigger that I was really happy to build and that seems to go over extremely well with our asmr community! The fishbowl effect, which I discovered after attending my first festival in 2008, appeared to have lingered with me and continues to do so. I've had a few requests for a "reverse" version, where instead of talking when it's off, just whisper while it's on. And that is exactly what I will do for you today!! Please, please! Settle back, unwind, and let's get started, family. Know that I Adore you with ALL of my being, and that I shall see you tomorrow”[9].

Figure 1.3. A 18 Minute video which relieves Anxiety and Panic attack [10].

Karuna Satori has quoted “It's been mentioned recently for an uneasiness/alarm help video. I've done recordings to assist with dying down those sentiments during an assault, and this is precisely the same kind of video - just utilizing an alternate methodology. Redirection. I start with control of sounds, sounds so light they are scarcely discernible (brushing). This has the psyche believing it's focusing on something significant, so amidst a heart dashing fit of anxiety - this can assist with fooling the brain into redirection to get your pulse down and concentrate somewhere else. That by itself won't stop a fit of anxiety generally, so I then utilize ordinary (yet light) finger snapping to put the psyche somewhere else too. The outline of this video is numerous redirections utilizing sound and visual feeling to remove survival during these assaults. I genuinely want to believe that you partake in this unique methodology family. Assuming that you realize anybody experiencing

these sentiments, they may possibly profit from this video or another ASMR type bit. So - sit back, unwind, and let me stunt to help your psyche. Realize I LOVE you, with The entirety of my individuality, and I will see you tomorrow!!” [10].

Discussion

In analyzing a research work it was found that, six graduate students (two men and four women) who were all familiar with ASMR films participated in the user experience research. They were instructed to perform two tasks using the suggested retrieval system:

(1) Find as many ASMR videos as you can, with the restrictions of no spoken language and for relaxation and soothing uses.

(2) It is simple to find satisfying ASMR videos.

Upon completion of each activity, the participants viewed the recovered films for 5-10 minutes to decide if they were satisfied with the findings.

Participants were then asked to respond to questions on the system usability scale (SUS) [12].

A study found evidence that watching ASMR films can lower heart rate and blood pressure. Unfortunately, the respiratory rate did not produce meaningful findings due to a number of reasons. Further study is required to pinpoint the precise impacts of watching ASMR recordings [13]. What is the ASMR then? This peculiarity depends on an unmistakable impression of tickling or on the other hand shivering that starts on the scalp and afterward drops down the neck zone and towards the spine. It can frequently cover the entire body, moving around it like a charming shudder. The individuals who have encountered this sensation depict it as an incredibly unwinding, agreeable, and wonderful feeling that can quiet you and your contemplations down, work on your fixation and rest, what's more, fundamentally upgrade your prosperity. ASMR can be brought about by various elements. The most normal incorporate hear-able, visual, olfactory, and material upgrades. Individuals going to an ASMR meeting are presented to the boosts referenced above, which are given by the craftsman running the meeting. Such an individual or gathering meeting can be directed live in an exceptional place like a health community, extraordinarily intended for the beneficiary and custom fitted to their requirements to guarantee unwinding of body and psyche. Nonetheless, the most famous type of ASMR content among the Murmur People group, or the local area watching and making ASMR content, are recordings posted on the web and the recordings draw the interest of scientists [14]. Skin-related feelings can be elicited by auditory events happening near to the head. While listening to binaural sounds with headphones, we may feel a tingling sensation over the scalp and back of the neck, which is known as the autonomous sensory meridian response (ASMR). Such cross-modal physical experiences can help researchers

better understand the underlying interplay between the auditory and somatosensory systems. Yet, it is unknown how auditory information influences body schema [15].

A research study which was analyzed explains how ASMR may be utilized in the promotion of slow tourist sites. It demonstrated the general compatibility of ASMR with slow tourism, as well as tips on how to put this compatibility into effect. Although several problems remain and the topic of ASMR marketing has to be further studied, the thesis has taken a first look at ASMR as a marketing tool by highlighting its applications for slow tourist locations [16]. As of late, an independent tactile meridian reaction (ASMR) is on the ascent socially and scholastically. It is a tactile peculiarity where individuals experience a shivering, static-like sensation because of explicit setting off sound or visual improvements . In reality many individuals have used ASMR to ease their pessimistic temperaments and prompt rest as it is frequently joined by sensations of quiet and unwinding . A concentrate on ASMR showed a diminished pulse and expanded skin conductance by focusing on an ASMR trigger (AT). This finding demonstrated that it could help mental and actual wellbeing . Another useful attractive reaction imaging concentrate on revealed that ASMR was connected with a mixing of various resting-state organizations . Despite the fact that ASMR studies have been led in later, they are as yet missing on the exploring physiological consequences for ASMR with the comprehension of changes in cerebrum designs. In this manner, it is expected to confirm the impacts of ASMR with the examination of cerebrum designs [17]. ASMR is an intriguing perceptual phenomena in which certain audio and visual stimuli cause a tingling sensation throughout the observer's head, neck, and shoulders, as well as a calming, pleasant emotional reaction. Millions of people have seen videos of strangers speaking, turning the pages of books, or opening and shutting lids, for example, to experience this sensory-emotional reaction, informally known as a brain orgasm [18].

Conclusion

The Systematic analysis indicates that Karuna Satori's ASMR videos are found to be therapeutic and are helping with the teenagers in reducing their stress, Depression and Anxiety levels.

References

- 1) Lokesh, E. S. Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response (ASMR) Helps In Rehabilitation For People Suffering From Anxiety, Depression And Stress–An Integrative.
- 2) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sfIDbyo-k3k>

- 3) Roberts, N. (2022). Autonomous sensory meridian response: induction, personality, and consciousness (Doctoral dissertation, Macquarie University).
- 4) Gillmeister, H., Succì, A., Romei, V., & Poerio, G. L. (2022). Touching you, touching me: Higher incidence of mirror-touch synaesthesia and positive (but not negative) reactions to social touch in Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response. *Consciousness and Cognition*, 103, 103380.
- 5) Lloyd, J. V., Ashdown, T. P., & Jawad, L. R. (2017). Autonomous sensory meridian response: What is it? and Why should we care?. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 39(2), 214-215.
- 6) Koumura, T., Nakatani, M., Liao, H. I., & Kondo, H. M. (2019). Deep, soft, and dark sounds induce autonomous sensory meridian response. *BioRxiv*, 2019-12.
- 7) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VT3LlzDpt0Y>
- 8) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qpaJEr638tQ>
- 9) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gnyn88h7jJM>
- 10) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZWq9Xv_9wvM
- 11) <https://www.youtube.com/@KarunaSatoriASMR/about>
- 12) Zhou, Q., Weng, J., & Xie, H. (2022, October). Find Your ASMR: A Perceptual Retrieval Interface for Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response Videos. In *HCI International 2022—Late Breaking Papers: HCI for Health, Well-being, Universal Access and Healthy Aging: 24th International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction, HCII 2022, Virtual Event, June 26–July 1, 2022, Proceedings* (pp. 215-225). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- 13) Idayati, R., Sufani, L., & Syahputra, D. A. (2021). Effect of watching autonomous sensory meridian response (AMR) video to heart rate, blood pressure and respiratory rate in students of Architectural Engineering, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Banda Aceh, Indonesia. *Bali Medical Journal*, 10(2), 733-736.
- 14) Łapińska, J. (2020). Creativity of human and non-human matter interwoven: Autonomous sensory meridian response videos in a posthuman perspective. *Creativity Studies*, 13(2), 336-350.
- 15) Tada, K., Ezaki, T., & Kondo, H. M. (2021). The Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response Activates the Parasympathetic Nervous System.
- 16) Bode, M. I. (2019). Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response (ASMR) as a marketing tool: an examination of the online phenomenon's potential in the promotion mix of slow tourism destinations.
- 17) Song, C. B., Kwak, N. S., Lee, M., & Lee, S. W. (2019, February). The effect of a binaural beat combined with autonomous sensory meridian response triggers on brainwave entrainment. In *2019 7th International Winter Conference on Brain-Computer Interface (BCI)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE.

Loki Falcon Tech Publishers, India.
Registered under MSME Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium
Enterprises. Udyam Registration No. UDYAM-TN-30-0007589

- 18) Glim, S., Braun, L., Hayd, S., Kuenz, A., Rosak, F., & Vom Bruch, J. (2022). Body scan meditation enhances the autonomous sensory meridian response to auditory stimuli. *Perception*, 51(6), 435-437.